

Blackhole Attack Detection and Mitigation in Wireless Networks: An advanced Paradigm¹

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Abstract

Wireless networks are adapted and functionally employed in a wide range of fields, and these networks are typically implemented in unprotected environments. As a result, they are susceptible to a wide variety of security risks, including black hole attacks, which can result in a network security breach. Research has been done on a variety of methods to detect and ward off an attack from a black hole. The numerous benefits and drawbacks of a wide variety of strategies are also explained, which assists in determining the most effective method for black hole assault. Real-time detection and mitigation of blackhole attacks still needs to be widely recognised. This research work focuses to establish an improved technique for black hole attack detection and prevention by proposing a hypothetical model. In regard with the defined objective, the study comprehended a developed technique integrating security trust approach enabled for dynamic systems aiding black hole attack detection and prevention. The results from descriptive analysis indicated that the proposed model can efficiently reduce the delay in the nodes and increase the network's performance.

Keywords

Black Hole Attack, Wireless Networks, Attack Detection, Security Trust, Dynamic Detection.

1. Introduction

Wireless networks, which provide users with seamless connectivity and mobility, have evolved to become an essential component of today's communication infrastructure. On the other hand, since

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these are decentralised and open, so are susceptible to a variety of security risks, including the blackhole attack. An example of a malicious conduct known as a blackhole attack is when a node in a network chooses which data packets to drop or trash, giving the impression to other nodes that it is a particularly desirable route (Dani et al., 2022).

The black hole attack is observed in which a malicious node waits for neighbouring nodes to forward route request (RREQ) signals. After the malicious node has accepted an RREQ message, it immediately sends the route reply (RREP) message of false copy to the sender with the maximum sequence number. This occurs before any other nodes send an actual true one (Salmi and Oughdir, 2023). It's essential to identify blackhole attacks in wireless networks and prevent them from disrupting data transmission and communication. One of the popular techniques to detect the presence of such attacks is to monitor on packet forwarding activity. Using a trust-based structure is another successful strategy to aid in prevention and detection attempts (Kumar et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Black hole attack overview (Talukdar et al., 2021)

The access point and network nodes receiving data packets from neighbour nodes with greater trust levels will continue the path and forward the data accordingly. A blackhole node, on the other hand, will display low trustworthiness due to its malevolent behaviour, resulting in lower trust values, which can be used to identify it. To eliminate the threat caused by blackhole attacks in wireless networks, it is equally important to establish strong mitigation measures in addition to effective detection.

2. Literature Review

Mobile Ad hoc NETWORKS (MANETs) do not directly fall within the infrastructure-based protection strategy that is often used for wireless networks. As a result, Moudni et al., (2019) introduced the Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS), which had a high detection rate and a low false alarm rate. To prevent and detect Black hole attacks, Talukdar et al., (2021) used an intrusion detection system (IDS) and a digital signature encryption approach.

In dense networks, this method improves the delivery ratio by 45.6%, whereas in sparse networks, it improves it by 41%. Additionally, it reduces missed packets in crowded networks by 75%. With the architecture incorporating a time series analysis of the dropped packets of each node, the Smart Blackhole and Grey Hole Mitigation (SBGM) programme was developed by Remya and Arun, (2022)

to detect and mitigate both black holes in the Vehicular Ad hoc Network, or VANET (a class of wireless networks). When compared to the prior methodologies, the employment of mobile agents with node authentication and trust values method boosted the packet delivery rate by 19.51%, cut energy consumption by 53.3%, and extended network life by 43.3%, according to Ashraf et al., (2023).

The majority of current blackhole attack detection techniques concentrate on offline analysis and a retrospective attack identification. It is essential to create algorithms and protocols that can quickly recognise and react to blackhole attacks in order to maintain network security and avoid lengthy outages.

3. Importance of methods for dynamic systems

Detecting black holes in real time is necessary for dynamic systems, particularly in settings in which the network architecture and the behaviour of nodes are known to often shift. According to the insights reported by (Kumar et al., 2021), dynamic systems are characterised by their continually evolving nature, where nodes can join and leave the network, and network connections can be made and broken in real-time. Examples of dynamic systems include mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) and Internet of Things (IoT) networks. Both types of networks are examples of dynamic systems.

In addition, traditional routing channels may become unavailable in dynamic systems because nodes may move out of range or experience link failures, rendering these routes inaccessible (Farahani, 2021). Because of the network's dynamic nature, it is susceptible to black hole assaults and may result in the frequent rediscovery of previously travelled routes. The detection of real-time black holes guarantees that routing decisions are continuously monitored and confirmed, thereby preventing malevolent nodes from setting up unauthorised routes and ensuring the integrity of the network.

4. Methodology

Considering the advanced paradigm development, the methodology proposed in this study adopts true node security technique and real-time detection for dynamic systems. Initially, it has been determined that the general-purpose ad hoc on-demand distance vector (AODV) based architecture should be regarded as an essential network protocol. From the insights obtained from the descriptive analysis, the significant methodology was identified, and the improvements are recommended for integration.

According to the framework shown in figure 2, the number of nodes inside the network is initialized as a primary task. Every node comes equipped with its very own buffer memory. During the process of data transmission, a message will be temporarily held in a memory known as a buffer. Following this, a message period, often known as TTL or Time-To-Leave, is set. Therefore, the time to live (TTL) is the amount of time it takes to convey a message, beginning with the production of the message by the source and ending with its delivery to the destination node. If the value has passed its expiration date, the message will be terminated. Now, a backbone node is initialised for the purpose of storing node routing information. After the routing information has been stored, the backbone node verifies each node by checking the information about the messages that each node has delivered.

Figure 2. Black hole detection and prevention architecture derived from Maheshavel and Senthilkumar, (2021); Talukdar et al., (2021)

5. Results and Discussion

The algorithm in this study has been focused to be feasible for dynamic and real time detection and also deterrence of Black hole attacks. No node in the network is identified inherently to behave as an attacker. As a result, in order to distinguish a malicious node from other nodes, this research work integrated the concept of an attacker node development. In recent years, there has been widespread consideration given to the security trust binary technique and fuzzy technique for the advancement of black hole attack detection in dynamic systems. For an instance, by utilising the K-nearest neighbour (KNN) technique for clustering and also fuzzy inference to choose the cluster head, Farahani, (2021) suggested a new algorithm for wireless networks to identify black hole attacks. As per the study, multihopping occurs in most wireless routing techniques where packets are routed by nodes acting as routers. Therefore, it is impossible to trust every node in the network for a task like routing. Due to relocation, especially in large networks, fuzzy systems, and neighbour node recognition among mobile nodes inside a wireless network are challenging to follow.

It is widely recognised that utilising continuous trust values in fuzzy techniques might result in a greater overhead in terms of the requirements for storage and communication; hence, security trust binary technique was considered to be studied for further research. Due to the fact that binary trust values representing the node entities, only need one bit to describe a node's trust level, they incur the least amount of cost in the security trust approach. Integrating the binary trust values with the network's routing protocols and security procedures is necessary for linking the security trust binary technique for real-time blackhole attack detection and prevention.

It is anticipated that the proposed hypothetical approach will have an efficient packet delivery ratio (PDR), delay, and also overhead are desirable and ensures a greater delivery ratio, along with lower

delay, and also lower overhead ratio compared to the conventional approach, in detecting and preventing those nodes from taking part in further communication.

6. Conclusion

The study proposed an improved hypothetical paradigm for Blackhole Attack Detection and Mitigation in Wireless Networks. The proposed technique integrated the security trust binary approach and real time detection of attack in dynamic systems. To ensure sustainable communication and data transfer in these networks, it is essential to identify and counteract such attacks. Numerous proposed techniques ensured that the above approach consumes less energy, however they were unable to lower the ratio of packet drops.

The proposed paradigm is foreseen for simulation evaluation and real time implementation in network systems. The proposed real time detection approach is anticipated to result with increased performance of the network. Hence, it is comprehended from this study that the timely identification of blackhole nodes with futuristic strategies including monitoring the behaviour of packet forwarding, trust-based systems, and machine learning algorithms can be advanced possible by the use of a variety of enhanced hybrid detection and prevention approaches.

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